

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE ANCESTORS HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL THINKING OF FUTURE SPECIALISTS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the development of professional thinking in future professionals on the example of the oldest priceless monument of our ancestors - "Avesto" on the basis of the "teacher-student" system relations

The problem of forming the personality of a future teacher is solved based on the needs and requirements of each individual society.

The heritage of our ancestors also reflects the interpretation of various doctrines and views of the mentality of our people on the ethno-pedagogical qualities, characteristics, qualities, abilities, methods of work, ways of achieving skills, and culture of interpersonal communication on the basis of teacher-student relations.

Indeed, traditions of the ancestors and the values of the past serve as an important tool in continuing the traditions of our statehood which have great historical and spiritual roots, the process of building a state based on democratic principles, including the development of young people as members of society. Our cultural heritage, the world's oldest and most

unique treasure trove of knowledge called "Avesto" reflects all the complex of sciences, fields, laws, ethical and social norms necessary for human development. Also, the essence of the spiritual and enlightenment world of Zoroastrians is the mention of the ideas of "good thought", "good word", "good deed" in the play on the basis of moral perfection, on the way to the development of "perfect man".

According to Zoroastrian teachings, the spiritual and moral perfection of every Mazdolik is determined by how well he performs his duties in Ahuramazda while facing the good, choosing the right path, studying worldly knowledge, and respecting his profession. After all, the Zoroastrian, who plowed the fields, sowed the grain, took care of the cattle, created a garden in the desert, dug up the soil, washed away the salt, and planted the crops, had a good character and good deeds.

In this article, we have tried to shed light on the content of the views of the teacher-student system and the duties and responsibilities of teachers in the texts of the Avesto in shaping the professional thinking of future teachers.

The basis of spiritual and moral education in the Avesto is the education and upbringing of pure, honest, pure-hearted, spiritually mature Zoroastrians, and the implementation of this task is entrusted to teachers and educators. When it comes to teachers, the Avesto first praises Ahura Mazda, the teacher of all teachers, the absolute deity: You have taught and educated about the benefits of Ashah-Truth and the harm of Duruj." It is clear from this that Yazdan is the creator of the universe and all the knowledge in the world, and Zoroaster is the one who conveys this knowledge to people and guides them to an enlightened future: "Mazda taught and Zoroaster reported" or "Mazda taught, let there be applause, joy and congratulations on the rejections of Zoroaster".¹

In Gohs and Yashts, Zoroaster is portrayed as a guide of teachers who continue the work of Yazdan, encouraging people to honesty, pure morality, and perfection. In the book, teachers and educators of the society are entrusted with the task of transmitting the teachings of Zoroaster to the next generation, spreading the rays of goodness to the world, and perfecting humanity on the basis of clear moral criteria. It was obligatory for the teachers to bring up brave, pure, knowledgeable students who would take Yazdan's duties to heart, apply them in their

work, work honestly for the prosperity and well-being of their homeland and protect it from enemies.

It is commendable that our ancestors 3,000 years ago developed the ways and principles of goodness and laid the foundation for the structure of the state and society: "Give me children who are harmonious and pious, patriotic and conciliatory, kind, kind-hearted, who save me from darkness and hardship. So that they can raise the address, the city, the country and its name and reputation."

In the Avesto, alongside with the basics of Zoroastrianism, the breeding of livestock, the creation of gardens (agronomy), the discharge of water into the desert, the washing of the soil with saline, the reclamation, the observation of celestial bodies, their movement and the calculation of day, year and time. visit (astronomy), rivers, mountains, regions, classification of countries (geography), protection of nature, environment (ecology, hygiene), protection of the country, people, livestock from enemies, pirates and giants (military knowledge), family structure, the fact that a complex of knowledge, such as male and female responsibilities, duties, duties (ethics, sociology) in the family and society, is described with great skill, shows that the monument has a huge literary, educational, encyclopedic value. It is noteworthy that it is a great responsibility for teachers to generalize and enrich this knowledge and pass it on to the next generation. At present, the development of directions, methods and techniques of teaching this knowledge in

¹ Ibid. 64 p.

schools and madrasas (pedagogics, didactics) is the task of wise teachers².

The Bible interprets the struggle of contradictory concepts and ideas, such as good and evil, light and darkness, truth and falsehood, beauty and ugliness, justice and injustice, on the basis of life and progress. The teacher and coaches, the ignorant and ignorant teacher, are portrayed as opposed to the coaches. At the same time, teachers and educators are divided into good and bad teachers, how much they know their knowledge, attitude to their profession, dedication, responsible approach to their duties. "The enlightened teacher warns the student" that is, a good teacher encourages his students to renounce vices such as ignorance of God, disbelief, dishonesty, selfishness, injustice, greed, immorality, incompetence and ignorance. He considers it his sacred duty to help him to display such qualities as honesty, integrity and piety, justice, and humanity. It is commendable to say of the Master, "In the light of truth, it leads to humility and happiness, and you have made this path a building for those who are aware of goodness."

At the same time, in the monument, bad teachers who sell their faith and knowledge to giants and durujs are severely criticized and condemned. "An evil educator, by his teaching, reverses the divine words and destroys the perception of life. In fact, it deprives people of the priceless investment of truth and good intentions" or "O, people who come from far and wide with the intention of acquiring knowledge! Now all of you listen, listen to

my clear words and keep in mind: never let a bad educator degrade your life, never let devious idiots mislead you with a deceptive language"³. Just as goodness (Ahura Mazda) always triumphs over evil and ignorance (Ahriman), so the teachings of wise teachers and mentors take precedence over the teachings of bad teachers, culminating in the development of students and disciples who inculcate good deeds in their hearts and minds.

The information in the question-and-answer monument during the reign of Shahanshah Khusrav II Parvez (591-628), a member of the Sassanid dynasty who adhered to the Zoroastrian religion, also helps to determine the level of professional thinking in the Zoroastrian education system.

It is said that the teenager, who belongs to a noble family, sits with his hands behind his back in a state of respect during a conversation with the emperor. The judge tests him by questioning him. During the exam, the teenager addressed the ruler and said: "Long live, O emperor, dreamer and citizen of the world ... My family has always been powerful, wealthy and grateful to the rulers ... At one time I was sent to school (farhangistan) and I was diligent in my studies. I memorized Yashts, Hadohn, Yasna, and Vandidod as harbed, and studied Zend (a medieval Persian commentary on the Avesto) in detail. I am good at writing (secular sciences), fiction and ... literary speech. When shooting from a bow, I am a sniper so that if my enemy leaves my arrow, he must consider himself lucky. I am so

² Абдуллаев К.Ф. Истоки Зороастризма. Монография. Челябинск. 2017 –с.80

³ "Авесто". Тарихий-адабий ёдгорлик. А. Маҳкам таржимаси –Т.: Шарқ нашриёти- матбаа концерни. 2001. -132 б.

strong in wrestling, horseback riding, horseback riding, fencing, spear handling that the opponent I face must consider himself unhappy. I am also the first in the competitions of Vin, barbat (musical instruments created by Borbad), drums and drums, singing and poetry. There is no one like me in the study and knowledge of stars, planets and celestial bodies. In chess and nevertashir (backgammon), hashtpad (eight-game game), my peers can't beat me. " Shahanshah tested the teenager on the best foods, drinks, clothing, music, plants, flowers, how well he knew the most thoroughbred horses, and how to behave in

public and at parties. The teenager answered all the questions intelligently and excellently, was awarded a gift, and was left in the service at the palace.⁴

Based on the teenager's own thinking and answers, it is commendable that he has mastered many areas of knowledge and professions. Indeed, the majority of members of society at that time reached maturity and perfection in almost all religious, secular, military, domestic and spiritual spheres. it should be noted that self-sacrifice was a major factor.

EDUCATIONAL STAGE:

⁴ Зороастрийские тексты. -Санкт-Петербург: «Нева», «Лесной сад». 1998. 102 с

Fig.1. Model of higher education in Zoroastrianism

At this point, we see that the involvement of future professionals in public affairs, depending on the level of knowledge, which guarantees the final result of higher education, is under the personal constant control and supervision of the supreme ruler⁵.

This situation shows how responsibly the ruler and public authorities have approached the process of training future professionals who will be directly involved⁶ in the future of public administration as a result of the management, support and implementation of measures to improve its quality.

The definition of teachers in the Avesta, the interpretation of teacher-student relations, the development of professional thinking of future professionals who will be involved in the affairs of state and society, has not lost its importance and value. At the same time, it is clear that the application of these ideas and views in the educational process, in the direction of spiritual and enlightenment education will be highly effective. This, in turn, requires a deeper, special study and analysis of the rich cultural, spiritual and educational heritage of our ancestors⁷.

⁵ Kurbanova G.N. Development of professional thinking through communicative skills among students of medical universities International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2019 Issue: 11 Volume: 79 Published: 30.11.2019 [http:// T-Science.org](http://T-Science.org)

⁶ Kurbanova G.N. Pedagogical and psychological bases on developing students' professional thinking in medical pedagogical education International

Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, Issue 06, 2020. 3059-3067 p.

⁷ Kurbanova G.N. The role of ancestral heritage in the development of professional thinking of future professionals International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2020 Issue: 01 Volume: 81 Published: 30.01.2020 <http://T-Science.org>. SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863

References

1. “Авесто”.Тарихий-адабий ёдгорлик. А. Маҳкам таржимаси –Т.: Шарқ нашриёти- матбаа концерни. 2001
2. Абдуллаев К.Ф. Истоки Зороастризма. Монография.Челябинск.2017 –с.80
3. Зороастрийские тексты. -Санкт-Петербург: «Нева», «Лесной сад». 1998.
4. Ҳомидов Ҳ. «Авесто» файзлари. -Т.: А.Қодирий номидаги Халқ мероси нашриёти. 2001
5. Kurbanova G.N. Development of professional thinking through communicative skills among students of medical universities International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2019 Issue: 11Volume: 79 Published: 30.11.2019 [http:// T-Science.org](http://T-Science.org)
6. Kurbanova G.N. Pedagogical and psychological bases on developing students' professional thinking in medical pedagogical education International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Vol. 24, Issue 06, 2020. 3059-3067 p.
7. Kurbanova G.N.The role of ancestral heritage in the development of professional thinking of future professionals International Scientific Journal
8. Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2020 Issue: 01 Volume: 81 Published: 30.01.2020 <http://T-Science.org>. SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863